

Some Reactions of Antimony Trichloride in N,N-Dimethylformamide

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Antimony trichloride forms 1 : 1 adduct with DMF (N,N-dimethylformamide) and its reactions in DMF have been studied conductometrically. With di- and triethylammonium chloride, potassium chloride, silver nitrate and potassium iodide, complex formation takes place. With bases like triethylamine and diethylamine, a quantitative solvolytic reaction occurs whereas with α -picoline and pyridine, adduct formation takes place. The solvolyzed products have been isolated and analyzed. These reactions throw light on the mode of ionization of antimony trichloride in DMF.

THE present investigation deals with some reactions of antimony trichloride with di- and triethylammonium chloride, silver nitrate, potassium iodide and some bases such as di- and triethylamine, α -picoline and pyridine using DMF as the medium. The technique for the studies is mainly conductometric titrations supported by the analysis of the precipitates isolated during the reaction and the supernatant solutions. The behaviour of the reactions supports the mechanism suggested in the earlier communications^{1,2} which is in harmony with the ideas of Drago and Purcell³ who evolved a coordination model for the nonaqueous solvent behaviour, and could not be understood by the mechanism suggested by Paul and coworkers⁴⁻⁶.

Experimental

Purification of DMF and bases : DMF and bases (di- and triethylamine, α -picoline and pyridine) were purified as described earlier¹.

Conductivity bridge and cell : A TESLA conductivity bridge was used. For measurements of low resistances a Shedlovsky type cell having a cell constant of 0.756 was used whereas for high resistance a cell containing electrodes of 1.25 cm² separated by 2 mm, having a cell constant of 0.12 was employed.

Infrared measurements : Infrared spectra of pure DMF, adduct of SbCl₃ with DMF and solvolyzed products were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 337 grating spectrophotometer as neat liquid or in nujol.

Conductivity titrations : Conductometric titrations were performed in the usual manner and the conductance after applying volume correction was plotted against the molar ratio (titrant/titrated substance).

Conductance in the molten state : Pure antimony trichloride and its adduct with DMF were separately taken in the conductance cell and melted using an oil bath. Resistance of the molten liquid and the temperature of the oil bath were measured.

Antimony trichloride adduct with DMF : Freshly distilled antimony trichloride (30.0 g) was added to excess of DMF (150 ml) cooled in an ice bath. The excess of DMF was removed by distillation under reduced pressure (35 mm pressure at 55 \pm 1°). White crystals of the product separated. These were washed with dry carbon tetrachloride and dry ether. The ether was finally removed under reduced pressure. The adduct melted at 46.5 \pm 1° and analyses of Sb, Cl and N were found to correspond to SbCl₃.HCON(CH₃)₂.

Isolation of the solvolyzed products of antimony trichloride in DMF with 0.5 mole and excess of di- and triethylamine (bases) : The precipitates were obtained by mixing requisite proportions of antimony trichloride in DMF and the base in DMF. The precipitates after being equilibrated were separated from the mother liquor, washed with dry carbon tetrachloride and finally with dry ether. The ether was removed under reduced pressure. The compounds so isolated corresponded on the basis of the analysis of Sb, Cl, and N to (1) SbCl₃·[CON(CH₃)₂]₂(C₂H₅)₃N, (2) SbCl₃·[CON(CH₃)₂]₂(C₂H₅)₃NH and (3) SbCl₃·[CON(CH₃)₂]₂·HCON(CH₃)₂. The melting points of the above compounds could not be determined as they decompose on heating.

IR of the solvolyzed product SbCl₃·[CON(CH₃)₂]₂·(C₂H₅)₃NH and SbCl₃·[CON(CH₃)₂]₂·HCON(CH₃)₂ : It is observed that the absorption frequency at 1676 cm⁻¹ in the case of DMF is affected when

complex formation takes place¹¹⁻¹³. The change in the spectra of these compounds from that of DMF is due to the lowering of the absorption frequency of >C=O group from 1670 cm^{-1} to 1625 cm^{-1} and this may be attributed to the replacement of hydrogen by more electropositive ion.

Isolation of the adducts of the $\text{SbCl}_3 \cdot \text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{N}$ and $\text{SbCl}_3 \cdot \text{C}_6\text{H}_7\text{N}$: Antimony trichloride (5g) was treated with purified and dried pyridine (50 ml) or α -picoline (50 ml) and refluxed for 2 hr. The clear supernatant solution was taken in another flask and excess of the base removed under reduced pressure. Solids obtained in either of the cases were washed with dry carbon tetrachloride and dry ether. The ether was finally removed under reduced pressure. The samples were analysed for Sb, Cl and N and found to correspond to $\text{SbCl}_3 \cdot \text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{N}$ and $\text{SbCl}_3 \cdot \text{C}_6\text{H}_7\text{N}$.

Methods of analysis: In the above compounds antimony was determined by titrating with potassium bromate using naphthol blue black as indicator, after dissolving the compounds in hydrochloric acid. Chlorine was determined gravimetrically as silver chloride after dissolving the compounds in nitric acid. Nitrogen was determined by Kjeldahl's method.

Results and Discussion

Reactions of antimony trichloride in DMF:

Antimony trichloride forms 1:1 solid adduct with DMF (m.p. $46.5 \pm 1^\circ$). Its solution in DMF has been used to study the reactions with di- and triethylammonium chloride, silver nitrate, potassium iodide and some bases which are discussed below.

Conductance behaviour:

The specific conductance of 0.05 M solution of antimony trichloride in DMF is $4.0 \times 10^{-4}\text{ ohm}^{-1}\text{ cm}^{-1}$ (25°) whereas those of antimony trichloride and DMF alone are $8.35 \times 10^{-7}\text{ ohm}^{-1}\text{ cm}^{-1}$ at 98° (the earlier reported value⁷ is $8.5 \times 10^{-7}\text{ ohm}^{-1}\text{ cm}^{-1}$ at 100°) and $1-3 \times 10^{-7}\text{ ohm}^{-1}\text{ cm}^{-1}$ at 25° , respectively. The increase in conductance on the dissolution of antimony trichloride in DMF indicates the occurrence of some ionization process in solution. The ionization can be explained by any one of the following mechanism.

(a) Mode of ionization according to the ideas of Paul and coworkers⁴⁻⁶:

(b) Mode of ionization according to the ideas proposed by the present authors¹:

The formation of other ionic species such as solvated $[\text{SbCl}]^{2+}$, $[\text{SbCl}_2]^{2-}$ and $[\text{Sb}]^{3+}$, $[\text{SbCl}_6]^-$ ions during ionization are considered unlikely as in solvent like DMF with a fairly low dielectric constant such ionic species would not be produced and if produced at all, they would aggregate to form ion-pairs.

According to mechanism (a), the formation of solvated ions would require atleast two mole of DMF per mole of SbCl_3 whereas in mechanism (b) the requirement is one mole of DMF per mole of SbCl_3 . The adduct $\text{SbCl}_3 \cdot \text{DMF}$ conducts in the molten state (sp. conductance $4.35 \times 10^{-5}\text{ ohm}^{-1}\text{ cm}^{-1}$ at 50°) and it is difficult to explain this by mechanism (a) as there is no extra DMF molecule to facilitate the ionization process. On the other hand the mechanism (b) easily explains the conductance of the adduct in the molten state and hence the formation of 1 : 1 adduct is more consistent with mechanism (b) than with (a). Further, the mechanism (a) represents solvolytic reaction and it is unable to explain the solvolytic products obtained by the reaction of bases discussed later.

The value of K, the thermodynamic dissociation constant, for various protonic and Lewis acids in DMF, obtained by Shedlovsky's method⁸, have been described elsewhere^{9,10}. The value of K for the system (b) may be given as follows:

$$K = \frac{C_{\text{SbCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{DMF}^+} \times C_{\text{SbCl}_4^-}}{C_{\text{Sb}_2\text{Cl}_6 \cdot 2\text{DMF}}} = 6.87 \times 10^{-8}$$

Fig. 1. Conductometric titration of 20.0 ml of 0.005M SbCl_3 with 0.1M triethylammonium chloride (curve 1), and diethylammonium chloride (curve 2).

Reaction with chlorides :

The conductometric titration curves (Fig. 1) of the reactions of antimony trichloride with di- and triethylammonium chlorides in DMF show a break at 1 : 1 molar ratio indicating the formation of $SbCl_4^-$ ion.

No precipitate appears and the solution remains clear. The formation of $[SbCl_4]^-$ ion is further supported by the fact that a solution of antimony trichloride in DMF dissolves an exactly equimolar quantity of potassium chloride, even though the latter is sparingly soluble in DMF.

Reaction with silver nitrate :

Silver nitrate dissolves readily in DMF and gives a white precipitate of silver chloride with a solution of antimony trichloride in DMF which is soluble in excess of antimony trichloride probably due to the formation of $AgSbCl_4$. The conductometric titration curve (Fig. 2) of the reaction of antimony trichloride with silver nitrate indicates two breaks, one

Fig. 2. Conductometric titration of 20.0 ml of 0.05M $SbCl_3$ with 1.0M $AgNO_3$ in DMF.

at 1 : 0.5 and the other at 1 : 3 molar ratios. The former break can be explained by the following reaction :

Reaction with potassium iodide :

Potassium iodide is fairly soluble in DMF whereas potassium chloride is sparingly so. It was expected that with antimony trichloride and potassium

iodide precipitation of potassium chloride would occur. It is observed experimentally that a complex formation reaction is superimposed over the precipitation reaction in the initial stages. When antimony trichloride is mixed with potassium iodide in DMF, initially no precipitate of potassium chloride appears but a yellow colour develops which gradually deepens to orange and finally to red as the concentration of iodide is increased. The precipitate of potassium chloride is visible only after three mole of potassium iodide for one mole of antimony trichloride has been added and the solution allowed to stand overnight. The reaction has been followed conductometrically and two sharp breaks at 1 : 1 and 1 : 3 molar ratios are observed, indicating the formation of $SbCl_2I^-$ and $SbCl_3I_3^{3-}$ (Fig. 3). Since no precipitate appears, complex ions are assumed to be formed (cf., 1,9).

Fig. 3. Conductometric titration of 20.0 ml of 0.05M $SbCl_3$ with 1.0M KI in DMF.

The metathetical reaction appears to be considerably slow as the precipitation of KCl is not immediately visible even after the addition of four moles of KI. But if such a solution is allowed to stand overnight the precipitate of KCl in accordance with the following reaction becomes visible and an appreciable change in conductance is also observed :

Reactions with bases :

When the solution of antimony trichloride in DMF is treated with bases such as di- and triethylamine a solvolytic reaction is observed and a white precipitate is obtained. This behaviour is exactly similar to that observed with bismuth trichloride¹. On analysis, the isolated precipitates have been

found to correspond to analogous compounds of bismuth obtained in a similar manner. These solvolytic reactions cannot be explained by the ideas of Paul and coworkers⁴⁻⁶. On the other hand these can be explained by the mechanism similar to that suggested for the solvolytic reactions of bismuth trichloride¹.

Antimony trichloride in DMF ionizes in the following way :

When the base is dissolved in DMF, the following equilibrium would exist :

When antimony trichloride and the base, both in DMF are mixed together, the reaction (1) occurs. This explains the peak at 1 : 0.5 molar ratio (Fig. 4).

Fig. 4. Conductometric titration of 20.0 ml of 0.05M SbCl_3 with 1.0M triethylamine (curve 1), diethylamine (curve 2), α -picoline (curve 3) and pyridine (curve 4) all in DMF.

The second break at 1 : 2 molar ratio can be explained by reaction (2).

The second stage of the reaction has also been studied conductometrically after preparing $\text{BH}^+ \cdot \text{SbCl}_4^-$ by an alternative reaction i.e. by mixing equal volumes of equimolar solutions of di- and triethylammonium chloride with antimony trichloride in DMF. The mixture was then titrated with di- or triethylamine, respectively (Fig. 5). The conductance decreases in the beginning and a break is observed at 1 : 2 molar ratio. A precipitate of $\text{SbCl}_2[\text{CON}(\text{CH}_3)_2] \cdot \text{B}$ is formed during the reaction.

Fig. 5. Conductometric titration of (curve 1) 10.0 ml of 0.05M SbCl_3 + 10.0 ml of 0.05 M $(\text{C}_2\text{H}_5)_3\text{NHCl}$ with 1.0 M triethylamine (curve 2) 10.0 ml of 0.05M SbCl_3 + 10.0 ml of 0.05 M $(\text{C}_2\text{H}_5)_2\text{NH}_2\text{Cl}$ with 1.0 M diethylamine in DMF medium.

The curves of these titrations are found to be similar to the portion of the curves (part AB in curves 1 and 2 in Fig. 4) representing the stage of the reaction which took place after the addition of 0.05 mole of the base. This not only supports the formation of SbCl_4^- ion in the first stage of the reaction but also indicates that a decrease of conductance would occur during the second stage of the reaction. This has been experimentally verified by measuring the conductance of equimolar solutions (0.05 M) of $[(\text{C}_2\text{H}_5)_2\text{NH}_2]^+\text{Cl}^-$ and $[(\text{C}_2\text{H}_5)_3\text{NH}_2]^+\text{SbCl}_4^-$. The conductance of the former (5.21×10^{-4}) is less than that of the latter (1.71×10^{-4}).

When titrations of antimony trichloride with bases such as α -picoline and pyridine in DMF are carried out, altogether different curves are obtained (Fig. 4; curves 3 and 4). The peaks observed at a molar ratio of 0.5 in the titrations with di- and triethylamine are absent in these curves whereas a break is observed at 1 : 1 molar ratio. No precipitate is observed during the reaction indicating that the solvolytic reaction is absent. This behaviour is different from that observed in analogous reactions of bismuth trichloride¹ where solvolytic as well as base displacement reactions take place simultaneously. In the present case, only a base displacement

ment reaction occurs and the break at 1 : 1 molar ratio may be explained by the following reaction :

During the above reactions antimony retains the coordination number of four and in this behaviour it differs from bismuth¹, as the coordination number of bismuth in analogous reactions is increased from four to six. To confirm this, adducts of antimony trichloride with α -picoline and pyridine by direct reaction in the absence of the DMF (solvent) were isolated. They were found to be in 1 : 1 ratio.

The above reactions further support the (b) mode of ionization of antimony trichloride in DMF. The conductance of a 0.1 M solution of antimony trichloride in pyridine is $3.2 \times 10^{-4} \text{ ohm}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ whereas that of the pure solvent is $4-5 \times 10^{-8} \text{ ohm}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$. The conductance of antimony trichloride in pyridine cannot be accounted for by mechanism (a) but may be readily explained by mechanism (b) according to which the following equilibrium may be postulated :

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